

5, 6 or 7-Substituted-3-phenyl-2(3H)-benzofuranones (III) were synthesised by reported methods⁶⁻⁷.

General procedure for the synthesis of 5, 6 or 7-substituted-3-phenyl-3(N,N-substituted aminomethyl)-2(3H)-benzofuranones (V₁₋₂₂): 3-Phenyl-2(3H)-benzofuranone (III) (0.002 mol) was stirred with para-formaldehyde (0.003 mol), conc. hydrochloric acid (2 ml) and appropriate secondary base (IV) (0.002 mol) in absolute alcohol for 30 min. Dry hydrogen chloride gas was bubbled through the reaction mixture for at least 20 min and then the mixture refluxed on a steam bath for 1-2 h. The reaction mixture was left overnight in ice. The product (V) was precipitated with dry acetone-ether (1:1 mixture) and recrystallised from alcohol.

Moderate to high yields (55-85%) of the products were recorded. Melting points and nitrogen content of the compounds are given in Table 1.

Pharmacological screening:-----

Albino mice were employed for pharmacological screening of the compounds prepared. All the experiments were conducted in triplicate and the mean values were taken.

(a) **Gross behavioural changes in mice:** Albino mice weighing 20-40 g each received intraperitoneally a suspension of each compound at the dose of 100 mg/kg. A few of the compounds under investigation could produce mild sedation and loss of righting reflex at this dose.

(b) **Hypnotic activity:** The compounds were screened for hypnotic activity by employing the standard method¹². The test compounds were administered to the mice intraperitoneally at a dose of 100 mg/kg and the effect on barbiturate hypnosis was recorded. The results are given in Table 1.

(c) **Anticonvulsant activity (MES):** Albino rats were screened for hind limb extensor after maximal electroshock (150 mA for 0.2 sec). Dilation was effective (78% protection) at the dose of 30 mg/kg. The test compounds, each at 100 mg/kg, were administered intraperitoneally. The results are recorded in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The ir spectra of 5, 6 or 7-substituted 3-phenyl-2(3H)-benzofuranones (III) showed a strong absorption in the 1790-1785 cm⁻¹ region. The higher carbonyl stretching vibration may be due to the β,γ -unsaturated γ -lactone system characteristic of 3-substituted-2(3H)-benzofuranones¹⁸. The pmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) of compounds (III) showed signals at δ 6.04-6.12 (s, 1H) and δ 7.08-7.67 (multiplet) assignable to the proton at 3-position and to aromatic protons, respectively.

The ir spectra of the Mannich bases (V) showed absorption in the 1770-1755 cm⁻¹ region indicating the carbonyl absorption shifting to lower frequency. The pmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) of compounds (V) exhibited signals at δ 4.05-4.17 (s, 2H) due to

-C-CH₂-N and at δ 6.98-7.46 assignable to aromatic protons. They showed the absence of the signal due to C₃-proton, observed in compound (III), confirming its substitution.

Perusal of Table 1 reveals that of the 22 compounds tested on gross behavioural changes in mice, 12 compounds (2, 4, 6, 7, 9, 10, 11, 13, 14, 17, 20 and 21) produced chronic convulsions. Almost all the compounds could produce a significant sedation indicating their CNS depressant activity. The results of the hypnotic activity test indicate that 12 compounds (2, 4, 7, 8, 9, 15, 16, 18, 19, 20, 21 and 22) significantly potentiated barbiturate hypnosis, while compound 5 significantly decreased the same. Twelve compounds (2, 4, 6, 9, 10, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 20 and 21) have been found to possess significant anticonvulsant activity against electroshock seizure test.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the authorities of Kakatiya University for facilities, Dr. V. P. Arya, Ciba Research Centre, Bombay for analysis and Drs. P. K. Das and S. N. Dube for pharmacological tests.

References

1. R. JAMES and G. ALBERT, *J. Pharmacol. Exp. Ther.*, 1944, **131**, 85.
2. R. K. RICHARDS, G. M. EVERETT and K. E. KUSTER, *J. Pharmacol.*, 1945, **38**, 387.
3. A. W. WESTON and W. M. BROWNELL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 563.
4. A. W. WESTON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 980.
5. A. BISTRZYCKI and J. FLATAU, *Chem. Ber.*, 1895, **28**, 989.
6. A. BISTRZYCKI and F. V. WEBER, *Chem. Ber.*, 1910, **43**, 2496.
7. H. V. LEIBIG, *Chem. Ber.*, 1908, **41**, 1644.
8. J. N. CHATTERJEA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **33**, 175.
9. H. E. ZAUGG, D. A. DUNNIGAM, R. J. MICHAELS, JR., R. J. SWETT, T. S. WANG, A. H. SOMMERS and R. W. DENET, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, **26**, 644.
10. A. SCHONBERG and A. MUSTAFA, *Chem. Rev.*, 1947, **40**, 181.
11. L. E. SMITH and R. N. HURD, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1957, **22**, 588.
12. R. A. TURNER, "Screening Methods in Pharmacology", Academic Press, N. Y., 1965, Vol. 1, p. 129.
13. W. H. WASHBURN, *Appl. Spectroscop.*, 1964, **18**, 61.

Studies on 4-Thiazolidinones. Part-I: Preparation and *in vitro* Antitubercular Activity of 4,4'-Bis-(2-Aryl-5-methyl-4-thiazolidinon-3-yl)-3,3'-Dimethyl biphenyl

B. R. PAREKH, N. A. LANGALIA and K. A. THAKER
Department of Chemistry, Bhavnagar University,
Bhavnagar-364 002

Manuscript received 17 May 1983, accepted 9 March 1984

THIAZOLIDINONES with various structural modifications possess diverse biological activities and numerous reports highlighting the chemistry and

TABLE I—DATA OF THE COMPOUNDS I AND II

No.	R	I	II	MIC $\mu\text{g/ml}$				
				0	25	50	100	150
1.	$-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$	142 ^a	162	-	-	-	-	-
2.	$2\text{-OH.C}_6\text{H}_4-$	200 ^a	186	-	-	-	+	+
3.	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\text{OH}=\text{CH}-$	190 ^a	181	-	-	-	-	-
4.	$4\text{-OCH}_3.\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-$	170 ^a	140	-	-	+	+	+
5.	$2\text{-Cl.C}_6\text{H}_4-$	150 ^a	242(d)	-	-	-	+	+
6.	$4\text{-Cl.C}_6\text{H}_4-$	165	115	-	+	+	+	+
7.	$4\text{-(CH}_3)_2\text{NC}_6\text{H}_4$	196	168	-	-	-	-	-
8.	$4\text{-OH-3-OH}_2\text{O-C}_6\text{H}_3$	188 ^b	80	-	+	+	+	+
9.	$4\text{-OH-3-CHO}_2\text{-5.NO}_2.\text{C}_6\text{H}_3-$	194	92	-	-	-	-	+
10.	$5\text{-Br-2-OH-C}_6\text{H}_3-$	215 ^b	242	-	+	+	+	+
11.	$3,5\text{-Di-Br-2-OH-C}_6\text{H}_3-$	202 ^b	256(d)	-	+	+	+	+
12.	$\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{O}$	190 ^b	110	-	-	-	-	-

MIC is the minimum inhibition concentration.

- Indicates no inhibition (inactive).

+ Indicates compound is active.

uses of thiazolidinones have appeared in the literature¹⁻⁴.

Several methods for the synthesis of 4-thiazolidinones have been reported¹⁻⁴. Of this, α -mercapto alkanic acids find extensive application and react conveniently with Schiff bases of aromatic or heterocyclic aldehyde/ketone and aliphatic or aromatic amines in different solvents to give a variety of substituted 4-thiazolidinones. The present communication reports the reaction of α -mercapto-propionic acid with *bis* anils (I) of a diamine *o*-toluidine and *in vitro* tuberculostatic activity of the resulting 4-thiazolidinones (II). The structure of (the compounds (I and II) were confirmed by elemental analysis and ir spectra.

Experimental

All m.p.s are taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected.

Preparation of 4,4'-bis-arylidene amino-3,3'-dimethyl biphenyl (I): An ethanolic solution of *o*-toluidine (0.05 mol; 10.6 g) and an appropriate aromatic heterocyclic aldehyde (0.11 mol) was refluxed in ethanol for 3 h, cooled and filtered. The product washed with cold ethanol and recrystallised from ethanol.

Preparation of 4,4'-bis-(2-aryl-5-methyl-4-thiazolidinon-3-yl)-3,3'-dimethyl biphenyl (II): To a solution of I (0.01 mol) in anhydrous benzene (25 ml) was added α -mercaptopropionic acid (2.34 ml, 0.022 mol), and the contents refluxed on a water bath for 15 h using a water separator, the solvent evaporated and the residue washed with aq. NaHCO_3 (2%) followed by CHCl_3 . The product was crystallised from EtOH.

The ir spectra of II showed the characteristic absorption bands at 1630 (s) and the 1200 to 1180 cm^{-1} region for thiazolidinone ring system.

Antimycobacterial activity:

The antimycobacterial activity of the compounds (II) have been studied against $\text{H}_8\text{7R}$ strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* in Lowenstein-Jensen's egg medium (5 ml). The retardation of growth rate was studied upto 6 weeks at 37°. The procedure was duplicated with solvent (DMF) for control.

It has been concluded from the experimental data that in contrast to 3,5-dibromo-2-hydroxy phenyl, 5-bromo-2-hydroxy-phenyl, 4-chloro-phenyl and 4-hydroxy-3-methoxy phenyl analogues the corresponding phenyl, 2-furyl, 5-nitro-4-hydroxy-3-methoxy phenyl, 4-dimethyl-amino-phenyl and cinnamyl analogues do not possess any significant tuberculostatic activity. The presence of halogen in the aryl moiety enhances the tuberculostatic activity.

The physical and biological data are presented in Table I.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Dr. S. B. Trivedi, Director, Tuberculosis Research Centre for antimycobacterial testing and the Bhavnagar University for Research Fellowship to one of them (B.R.P.).

References

1. F. C. BROWN, *Chem. Rev.*, 1961, 61, 468.

2. K. A. ZOLOTOROVA, I. P. MASLOVA, N. A. GLAZU NOVA, E. F. BURMISTROV and L. A. PUGACHEVA, *Voronesh*, 1964, 5 (*Chem. Abst.*, 1966, 65, 18767).
3. G. DANILA, *Rev. Chim. (Bucharest)*, 1978, 29, 820, 1152 (*Chem. Abst.*, 1979, 90, 72086, 152037).
4. S. P. SINGH, S. S. PARMAR, K. RAMAN and V. I. STENBERG, *Chem. Rev.*, 1981, 81, 175.
5. U. H. PANDYA, R. R. ASTIK and K. A. THAKER, *Chemical Era (India)*, 1978, 14, 485.

Preparation of Some Thiazolidinone and Their Benzoyl Derivatives and Study of Their Antimicrobial Activity

S. V. PATEL, J. N. VASAVADA and G. B. JOSHI*

Department of Chemistry, Bhavnagar University,
Bhavnagar 364 002

Manuscript received 10 March 1982, revised 10 November 1983,
accepted 27 February 1984

PHENOLS possess antiseptic¹, germicidal², anti-fungal³, antibacterial and other biological activities. 4-Thiazolidinones are also associated with various biological activities⁵⁻⁷. 4-Thiazolidinones of type (I) containing phenol residue were obtained by the action of thioglycolic acid, thiolactic acid or thiomalic acid on Schiff bases which in their turn were obtained by the reaction of 2-hydroxy-3-bromo-5-methyl benzophenone⁸ with different sulpha drugs. The constitution was supported by ir spectra^{9-11,12}. The products were screened for antimicrobial activity.

I

R = H, 4'-methyl pyrimidyl, 4',6'-dimethyl pyrimidyl, 2'-thiazolyl, 3',4'-dimethyl oxazolyl.

R₁ = H, OH, CH₃, COOH.

R₂ = H, COC₆H₅.

R₃ = H, Br.

IR spectra :

The ir spectra of 4-thiazolidinones (I) were taken on KBr pellets. The $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ was obtained at 1640 and $\nu(\text{N}-\text{CO})$ at 1590, $\nu(\text{phenolic}-\text{OH})$ at 3410 and $\nu(\text{NHSO}_2)$ at 1150 cm^{-1} .

Experimental

Preparation of α -phenyl-2-hydroxy-3-bromo-5-methyl benzalanil/2-benzoate¹⁴ : 2-Hydroxy-3-bromo-5-methyl benzophenone (0.01 mol) dissolved in ethanol was added to sulphanilamide (0.01 mol) in ethanol and refluxed on a waterbath for 6 h and the content poured into water. The product was isolated

and crystallised from ethanol. The anils were benzoylated by the treatment of benzoyl chloride and 10% cold sodium hydroxide solution. The product (R₂ = H) was poured on ice, separated and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 86°, yield 80% (Found : C, 53.90 ; H, 3.76 ; N, 6.22. C₂₀H₁₇O₂N₂SBr requires C, 53.93 ; H, 3.82 ; N, 6.29%).

Similarly, other anils were prepared by condensing ketones with sulphadimidine, sulphamethazine, sulphathiazole and sulphaoxazoles. Their benzoyl derivatives were also prepared.

Preparation of α -phenyl-2-(2'-hydroxy-3'-bromo-5'-methyl phenyl)-3-p-amino sulphophenyl-4-thiazolidinone : α -Phenyl-2-hydroxy-3-bromo-5-methyl benzalanil/2-benzoate (0.01 mol) in benzene was refluxed with thioglycolic acid (0.01 mol) on a water bath for 4 h. The product was isolated and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 93°, yield 72% (Found : C, 50.81 ; H, 3.23 ; N, 5.33. C₂₂H₁₆O₄N₂S₂Br requires C, 50.86 ; H, 3.28 ; N, 5.39%).

Similarly, other anils and their benzoyl derivatives were treated with thioglycolic acid.

Preparation of α -phenyl-2-(2'-hydroxy-3'-bromo-5'-methyl phenyl)-3-p-aminosulphophenyl-5-methyl-4-thiazolidinone : Thiolactic acid (0.01 mol) was added to a solution of α -phenyl-2-hydroxy-3-bromo-5-methyl benzal anil (0.01 mol) in dry benzene (25 ml) and refluxed for 6 h. The product was isolated and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 76°, yield 61% (Found : C, 57.71 ; H, 3.90 ; N, 5.22. C₂₈H₂₁O₄N₂S₂Br requires C, 57.78 ; H, 3.94 ; N, 5.25%).

Similarly, other anils and their benzoyl derivatives were treated with thiolactic acid.

Preparation of α -phenyl-2-(2'-hydroxy-3'-bromo-5'-methyl phenyl)-3-p-aminosulphophenyl-5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinone : α -Phenyl-2-hydroxy-3-bromo-5-methylbenzal anil (0.01 mol) was condensed with thiomalic acid (0.01 mol) in presence of anhydrous zinc chloride (0.5 g) at 160° for 30 min (Reddellien method¹³). The product was dissolved in sodium bicarbonate and reprecipitated with acid and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 70°, yield 58% (Found : C, 49.79 ; H, 3.58 ; N, 4.79. C₂₄H₂₁O₆N₂S₂Br requires C, 49.91 ; H, 3.64 ; N, 4.85%).

Similarly, other anils and their benzoyl derivatives were treated with thiomalic acid.

Antimicrobial screening :

The purified products were screened for antimicrobial activity by cup plate method¹⁵ using *S. aureus* (gram +ive) and *E. coli* (gram -ive). Ethanolic solutions of the compounds were used for the tests. The zones of inhibition for the test solution containing 0.5 mg of the compound were recorded. The anils are active* against *S. aureus* and moderately active to inactive against *E. coli*. Most of the 4-thiazolidinones are highly active* against *S. aureus* but are inactive against *E. coli*.

* Present address : Department of Chemistry, Saurashtra University, Rajkot-360 005.

* Details of activity tests may be obtained from the author on request.